

Spectrum of Radiographic Findings in Pulmonary and Extrapulmonary Tuberculosis: A Literature Review

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Abstract

Tuberculosis remains a major global health problem and a leading cause of death from a single infectious agent. Because clinical manifestations are often nonspecific, imaging is central to early detection, diagnosis, evaluation of disease extent, and identification of complications in both pulmonary and extrapulmonary tuberculosis. This review summarizes the radiologic features of tuberculosis across organ systems and imaging modalities relevant to radiology practice. Chest radiography remains the first-line examination for pulmonary tuberculosis, although its sensitivity for lymphadenopathy and early parenchymal disease is limited. Computed tomography is superior for detecting lymphadenopathy, cavitation, endobronchial spread, miliary disease, and disease activity. Ultrasound provides practical bedside assessment, particularly for pleural, abdominal, and selected extrapulmonary manifestations, whereas magnetic resonance imaging is especially useful for central nervous system, spinal, and genitourinary involvement because of its high soft tissue contrast and lack of ionizing radiation. Extrapulmonary tuberculosis commonly involves lymph nodes, meninges, the gastrointestinal tract, the hepatosplenic system, the genitourinary tract, and the musculoskeletal system. Recognition of imaging patterns such as necrotic lymphadenopathy, basal meningeal enhancement, ileocecal thickening, putty kidney, paraspinal abscess, and vertebral destruction can reduce diagnostic delay, improve treatment planning, and help prevent irreversible complications, especially in endemic settings and immunocompromised patients.

Keywords: tuberculosis; radiologic imaging; pulmonary tuberculosis; extrapulmonary tuberculosis; computed tomography

Background

Worldwide, tuberculosis (TB) remains the leading cause of death from a single infectious agent (World Health Organization, 2023), including among people living with human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) (R. K. Gupta et al., 2015). The World Health Organization (WHO) End Tuberculosis Strategy set ambitious targets for 2020-2035, including a 20% reduction in TB incidence and a 35% reduction in the absolute number of TB deaths by 2020, as well as a 90% reduction in TB incidence and a 95% reduction in TB deaths by 2035, compared with 2015 levels (World Health Organization, 2023).

TB is caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* bacilli, which spread when individuals with TB release bacteria into the air, for example by coughing. Approximately one quarter of the global population is estimated to have been infected with TB (Menzies et al., 2018). After infection, the risk of developing active TB disease is highest during the first 2 years, at approximately 5%, and becomes much lower thereafter (World Health Organization, 2023). Some individuals clear the infection spontaneously (Behr et al., 2019; Emery et al., 2021). Of all people who develop TB each year, about 90% are adults, and cases are more common in men than in women. TB most commonly affects the lungs as pulmonary TB, although it can also involve other organs (Behr et al., 2019).

Without treatment, the mortality rate of TB is high, at approximately 50% (Tiemersma et al., 2011). With current WHO-recommended treatment using anti-TB drugs for 4-6 months, about 85% of patients can be cured. Regimens of 1-6 months are also available for TB infection treatment. Universal health coverage is needed to ensure access to treatment for everyone with TB disease or infection. The number of people infected and progressing to active disease, and consequently the number of TB-related deaths, can also be reduced through multisectoral interventions that address major TB determinants such as poverty, malnutrition, HIV infection, smoking, and diabetes (World Health Organization, 2023).

Clinical manifestations of TB include fever, night sweats, unexplained weight loss, loss of appetite, and fatigue. Persistent cough, with or without hemoptysis, dyspnea, and pleuritic chest pain are additional manifestations in

patients with highly infectious pulmonary TB. However, clinical manifestations of extrapulmonary TB vary according to the organ involved. Therefore, the diagnosis of extrapulmonary TB requires a high index of suspicion, as well as further laboratory and radiologic evaluation (Tan et al., 2010).

Medical imaging plays a major role in detecting tissue abnormalities and supporting the presumptive diagnosis of TB. Conventional radiography, computed tomography (CT), ultrasonography, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and positron emission tomography CT (PET-CT) all contribute to TB diagnosis and can help clinicians identify disease in different body regions. Various forms of TB, including pulmonary, abdominal, scrotal, cerebral and spinal, and musculoskeletal (MSK) TB, can be evaluated using different imaging modalities (Alshoabi et al., 2022). This review discusses the general radiologic features of pulmonary and extrapulmonary TB using radiographic imaging modalities.

Radiology for Tuberculosis

Early diagnosis is one of the key strategies for TB control. However, sputum examination has an accuracy of only about 50% and often misses disease in its early stage. Systematic screening strategies are therefore needed to ensure early and accurate diagnosis in all individuals with TB, and chest X-ray (CXR) remains one of the main tools for TB screening. Although various methods are available to diagnose TB, each has limitations and may result in missed cases. Limited access to advanced diagnostic tests contributes to suboptimal detection performance. Delayed diagnosis and misdiagnosis increase patient morbidity and mortality and allow continued TB transmission (Noviyani et al., 2021; Parwati et al., 2020).

Pulmonary Tuberculosis

Tuberculosis is an infectious disease caused by straight or slightly curved rod-shaped bacteria that are non-spore-forming, non-encapsulated, and acid-fast, known as *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. The clinical presentation of pulmonary TB includes productive cough for at least 2 weeks, with additional symptoms such

as hemoptysis, dyspnea, weakness, loss of appetite, weight loss, night sweats, and other manifestations that may resemble those of other diseases. Therefore, radiographic examination is needed for early detection and further diagnosis of tuberculosis (PDPI, 2021).

The manifestations of primary pulmonary tuberculosis include gangliopulmonary TB, characterized by air-space consolidation and lymphadenopathy, pleural effusion, miliary disease, and tracheobronchial TB. Only the gangliopulmonary form is characteristic of primary TB, whereas the other manifestations may also be seen in post-primary disease (PDPI, 2021).

The standard radiologic examination for pulmonary TB is chest radiography in the posteroanterior (PA) projection. Other examinations may be performed based on clinical indications, such as lateral, apical lordotic, or oblique chest radiographs, as well as CT. On chest radiographs, tuberculosis may produce a wide range of appearances (PDPI, 2021).

Radiographic Modalities

A. Chest X-Ray

Chest radiography is the primary radiologic examination in children for the diagnosis and assessment of pulmonary tuberculosis (PTB) (De Villiers et al., 2004; Pillay et al., 2020). Radiographic findings closely reflect the pathophysiology of the disease (Concepcion et al., 2017). A parenchymal focus associated with lymphadenopathy, known as the Ghon complex, is often small and difficult to identify on chest radiographs.

The sensitivity of chest radiography for detecting lymphadenopathy, compared with CT imaging, has been reported to be 67-74%, with a specificity of 39-59% (Concepcion et al., 2017; Sodhi, Bhalla, et al., 2017; Swingler et al., 2005). The value of lateral chest radiography in improving sensitivity or specificity remains controversial. One study found that adding a lateral radiograph to the frontal view did not significantly improve diagnostic performance, while it increased both cost and radiation exposure (Swingler et al., 2005). In another study, a moderate correlation was demonstrated between lymphadenopathy findings on lateral chest radiographs and CT scans, with preclavicular lymph

nodes showing the highest sensitivity and specificity (Andronikou et al., 2012). Detection of lymphadenopathy on chest radiography also shows substantial interobserver variability, with a mean weighted kappa of 0.33-0.36, and poor intraobserver agreement, with a mean weighted kappa of 0.55 (Nel et al., 2022)

B. Ultrasound

Ultrasonography allows trained clinicians to make rapid diagnostic and management decisions at the bedside. A major advantage of ultrasound is its ability to assess features of extrapulmonary tuberculosis, including ascites, hepatic microabscesses, pericardial effusion, and abdominal lymphadenopathy. Ultrasonographic abnormalities suggestive of PTB, such as consolidation, pleural effusion, or lymphadenopathy, can be found in 31% to 83% of confirmed cases, with high inter-reader agreement (Bélard et al., 2018; Heuvelings, Bélard, Andronikou, et al., 2019). Diagnostic accuracy improves with operator experience (Heuvelings, Bélard, Familusi, et al., 2019). However, data on the sensitivity and specificity of ultrasound for PTB remain limited. Most studies have compared ultrasound with chest radiographic findings. This makes assessment of diagnostic accuracy difficult because chest radiography itself has limited accuracy. The use of clinical diagnosis as a reference standard has similar limitations. Comparison with gold-standard imaging techniques, such as CT, would provide valuable information regarding the role of ultrasound in the diagnosis and management of PTB (Heuvelings, Bélard, Andronikou, et al., 2019).

Based on the study by Fentress et al. in 2020, a high proportion of patients with tuberculosis in the study, 96.1%, had composite consolidation or subpleural consolidation detected on lung ultrasound (LUS). Although subpleural consolidation, defined as hypoechoic, nodular subpleural lesions usually measuring less than 1 × 1 cm, has also been described in other conditions such as pulmonary embolism, viral pneumonia including COVID-19, Pneumocystis pneumonia, and early bacterial pneumonia, the data suggest that these sonographic lesions are frequently encountered in the patchy fibronodular infiltrates commonly seen in PTB. Lung ultrasound detects lesions that extend to the pleural line, and most acute pulmonary abnormalities reach the pleural line,

including 98.5% of acute consolidations observed on chest computed tomography in critically ill patients (Fentress et al., 2020).

C. Computed Tomography Scan (CT-Scan)

CT is considered the gold standard for imaging primary pulmonary tuberculosis. Cross-sectional images and three-dimensional image processing provide excellent anatomic detail and overcome the problem of overlapping anatomic structures seen on chest radiographs. CT enables earlier and more frequent detection of lymphadenopathy, consolidation, and pleural effusion compared with chest radiography (Concepcion et al., 2017; Lucas et al., 2012). In addition, CT allows more accurate assessment of disease process, disease activity, and the detection of complications. CT is particularly effective for characterizing lymph nodes. The presence of calcification, although uncommon, within lymph nodes is highly suggestive of tuberculosis (Peng et al., 2011). Enhancement patterns in lymphadenopathy may help distinguish PTB from other diseases. Tuberculous nodes typically show ring enhancement, indicating central caseous necrosis, or ghost-like enhancement within an ill-defined nodal mass (Andronikou et al., 2004; Peng et al., 2011). Parenchymal lung complications distal to lymph node compression follow a predictable stepwise course. These findings can be staged by CT to determine whether the lung is salvageable or non-salvageable (Andronikou et al., 2021). Staging can guide medical therapy and determine whether surgical intervention is required, such as enucleation of the affected lymph nodes or lobectomy in non-salvageable lung tissue.

According to Buonsenso, D. et al., comparison between CT and chest X-ray in detecting pulmonary TB cases based on the proposed radiologic probability criteria demonstrated the superiority of CT in identifying probable TB imaging findings, with 70.3% compared with 36.6% for chest X-ray. The study also found that 7 of 41 patients, or 17.1%, with normal chest X-rays showed abnormalities on CT. In both cases, the differences were statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). In addition, hilar or mediastinal adenopathy was identified in 89.2% of CT scans, 33 of 37, whereas it was seen in only 36.6% of chest X-rays, 15 of 41 (Buonsenso et al., 2021).

D. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), although more expensive and less widely available than other imaging modalities, is free of ionizing radiation and is an ideal examination for follow-up evaluation (Kapur et al., 2019; Sodhi et al., 2022; Sodhi, Sharma, et al., 2017). In the past, the long MRI acquisition time required children to undergo sedation or anesthesia for the procedure. However, the development of rapid MRI sequences, with acquisition times of 10-20 seconds per sequence (Sodhi et al., 2022), has made MRI a more attractive examination, especially in children, because it can be performed without sedation (Sodhi, Sharma, et al., 2017). MRI is comparable to CT in diagnosing primary pulmonary tuberculosis (Sodhi et al., 2022).

Radiologic Patterns

Primary Pulmonary TB

Primary TB radiologically manifests as four main entities: dense homogeneous consolidation, predominantly in the middle and lower lobes, lymphadenopathy, miliary disease, and pleural effusion (Burrill et al., 2007). Lower lobe disease, adenopathy, and pleural effusion are common in children but less common in adults. Therefore, these findings are considered atypical in adults, whereas upper lobe disease seen in most adults is regarded as typical reactivation tuberculosis. Upper lobe cavitory disease is usually seen in infected immunocompetent hosts, whereas immunocompromised patients more often present with lower lung disease, adenopathy, and pleural effusion (Rozenstein et al., 2015). In the pediatric population with active TB, upper lobe predominance has been identified in 36-82% of cases and is associated with lymphadenopathy in up to 15% of cases (Miranda-Schaeubinger et al., 2023). The imaging appearance of active PTB does not depend on the time since infection (Jones et al., 2012; Rozenstein et al., 2015) and therefore cannot reliably distinguish primary from secondary disease.

Tuberculoma (Figure 1) is a pulmonary nodule and may be the only abnormality visible on chest radiography in approximately 5% of patients with active TB (Sari et al., 2019). Satellite nodules surrounding the tuberculoma, which

usually has smooth and sharply defined margins, may be seen in up to 80% of cases. When solitary, an active tuberculoma may be mistaken for malignancy.

Figure 1. A 37-year-old woman underwent routine chest radiography (a), which showed a solitary pulmonary nodule in the left mid-lung zone (arrow). CT of the lungs in the axial plane (b) confirmed a 27 mm nodule in the lingula (arrow) with adjacent small satellite nodules (arrow), without lymphadenopathy. Sputum acid-fast bacilli smear was negative, but TB culture from bronchoalveolar lavage was positive for *M. tuberculosis* (Alshoabi et al., 2022).

Lymphadenopathy (Figure 2) is the most common radiologic manifestation of primary TB. It is characterized by enlargement of the paratracheal, hilar, or subcarinal lymph nodes, with or without parenchymal abnormalities. Lymphadenopathy is more common in children than in adults and may cause pulmonary atelectasis. CT is more effective than chest X-ray (CXR) for detecting lymph nodes, which typically show low central attenuation and peripheral enhancement after contrast administration, forming the rim sign (Bhalla et al., 2015a; Nachiappan et al., 2017). Bilateral hilar lymphadenopathy is an important differential diagnosis for many benign and malignant diseases, such as sarcoidosis and lymphoma.

Figure 2. Primary TB in an 18-year-old man. Axial CT image in the mediastinal window shows multiple enlarged mediastinal lymph nodes (short arrows), and a right hilar lymph node with low central attenuation and peripheral enhancement after contrast administration, forming the rim sign (long arrow) (Alshoabi et al., 2022).

Parenchymal disease (Figure 3) is another radiologic pattern of primary TB and most commonly appears as consolidation distributed as segmental or lobar opacities. However, a strong lobar predilection and cavitation are not typical features of primary TB.

Figure 3. Active TB in a 27-year-old man with extensive endobronchial spread. Selected axial chest CT images show extensive endobronchial spread with patchy consolidation (long arrows) in the right middle and left lower lobes, and tree-in-bud nodules (short arrows), more extensive in the left lung. Mild right pleural effusion and mild pericardial effusion are also present on both images (Alshoabi et al., 2022).

Post-primary Pulmonary TB

Post-primary TB occurs in previously sensitized patients, either from reinfection or reactivation of dormant bacilli from a primary infection, and usually affects adolescents and adults. It typically involves the apical and posterior segments of the upper lobes and the superior segments of the lower lobes. It is characterized by liquefaction of caseous necrosis with cavity formation, progressive fibrosis and lung destruction, and bronchogenic spread (Bhalla et al., 2015b). Radiologic features suggesting active TB include centrilobular nodules, bronchial wall thickening, poorly defined nodules, thick-walled cavities, lobular consolidation, pleural effusion, miliary nodules, and necrotic lymph node enlargement (K. S. Lee et al., 2013; Skoura et al., 2015). In contrast, thin-walled cavities, pulmonary fibrosis, pleural thickening, calcified or non-calcified nodules, and parenchymal or pleural calcifications may indicate prior infection (Skoura et al., 2015; Uzorka et al., 2019).

Classic CT findings of post-primary PTB include centrilobular nodules, the tree-in-bud pattern, consolidation, ground-glass opacity, cavitation, bronchial wall thickening, miliary nodules, isolated pulmonary nodules, parenchymal bands, and interlobular septal thickening. Several common patterns may be seen in post-primary pulmonary TB (Wetscherek et al., 2022):

Consolidation (Figure 3) is one of the most common findings of post-primary TB. It is usually focal, patchy, heterogeneous, or ill defined, and typically involves the apical and posterior segments of the upper lobes and the superior segments of the lower lobes (Skoura et al., 2015). Consolidation with ipsilateral hilar or paratracheal lymph node enlargement may suggest TB. CT is more sensitive for detecting small and subtle tuberculous consolidations, which are usually peribronchial or subpleural and often involve multiple lung segments (Bhalla et al., 2015b).

Figure 4. Post-primary TB in a 45-year-old man with cough and hemoptysis.

Axial chest CT images show (a) cavitory lesions in the right upper lobe and superior segment of the left lower lobe, surrounded by consolidation; (b) a thick-walled irregular cavity in the superior segment of the left lower lobe, surrounded by patchy ground-glass opacity; (c) centrilobular nodules and tree-in-bud nodules; and (d) left lower lobe consolidation with air bronchograms (Alshoabi et al., 2022).

Cavitation (Figures 3 and 4) is a common finding in post-primary TB and usually appears as cavities several centimeters in size with thick, irregular walls. Cavities often develop within areas of consolidation and may persist after treatment, predisposing to bacterial or fungal superinfection or erosion of adjacent vessels that can cause hemoptysis (K. S. Lee et al., 2013; Nachiappan et al., 2017). In post-primary TB, consolidation and cavitation usually involve the apical and posterior segments of the upper lobes and the superior segments of the lower lobes (Nachiappan et al., 2017). This distribution likely reflects relatively increased ventilation, high oxygen tension, and delayed lymphatic clearance in these regions (Nemec et al., 2013). Thick-walled cavities should be differentiated from lung abscess, septic emboli, aspergilloma, granulomatosis with polyangiitis, and pulmonary malignancy (Parkar & Kandiah, 2016).

Figure 5. Reactivation TB in a 34-year-old woman. (a) Chest radiograph shows extensive reticular opacities and multiple cavitary lesions in both lungs. (b) Coronal CT reconstruction shows multiple cavitary lesions in both lungs, with the largest in the posterior segment of the upper lobe and the apical segment of the left lower lobe. (c, d) Axial lung CT images show multiple cavities, largest in the posterior segment of the left upper lobe, with associated centrilobular nodules (long arrows) and tree-in-bud opacities (short arrows) (Alshoabi et al., 2022).

Centrilobular nodules (Figures 4 and 5) result from communication between active TB and the bronchial tree, causing endobronchial spread. They are present in most cases of active TB. On CT, they appear as centrilobular nodules and tree-in-bud opacities (Bomanji et al., 2015; Nachiappan et al., 2017). On high-resolution CT, the tree-in-bud pattern appears as 2-4 mm centrilobular soft-tissue nodules connected to branching linear structures of similar caliber arising from a single stalk. This pattern commonly reflects endobronchial spread and strongly suggests active TB. However, tree-in-bud is not specific and may also be seen in other lung diseases, including cytomegalovirus infection, respiratory syncytial virus infection, bronchiolitis obliterans, diffuse panbronchiolitis, cystic fibrosis, invasive airway aspergillosis, allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis, and pulmonary metastases (Rossi et al., 2005).

Pattern Variants

Miliary TB (Figures 6 and 7) appears as innumerable small granulomas, 1-3 mm in size, with random distribution in the lungs and other organs, often with basal predominance due to gravity-dependent blood flow. It results from hematogenous spread of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, especially in immunocompromised patients and children (Bhalla et al., 2015b; Nachiappan et al., 2017). Miliary TB is an important differential diagnosis of pulmonary metastases, particularly from thyroid cancer and other malignancies, including in children.

Figure 6. A 44-year-old woman presented with malaise, loss of appetite, vomiting, and fever. She had been diagnosed with HIV 2 months earlier but was nonadherent to antiretroviral therapy. Her CD4 count at presentation was 110 cells/mm³. CT shows miliary nodules (lung window, coronal plane, maximum intensity projection, a) and an enlarged right paratracheal node with low central attenuation (mediastinal window, coronal plane, b, arrow), consistent with necrosis (Wetscherek et al., 2022).

Characteristic findings of tracheobronchial TB include irregular circumferential wall thickening with luminal narrowing. Isolated tracheal disease is rare. Most patients present with involvement of the distal trachea, carina, and proximal main bronchi (Restrepo et al., 2016; Yeon & Lee, 2008). Tracheobronchial disease frequently coexists with lymphadenopathy in active pulmonary TB (Restrepo et al., 2016). In tracheobronchial TB, peribronchial lymphatic spread appears more common than endobronchial spread from infected sputum. Bronchial stenosis occurs in 10% to 40% of patients with active TB (Burrill et al., 2007; Ravenel et al., 2017) and may cause segmental or lobar atelectasis, lobar

hyperinflation, mucoid impaction, and post-obstructive pneumonia (Nachiappan et al., 2017).

Figure 7. A 35-year-old man presented with a 4-week history of productive cough, anorexia, and weight loss. Initial CT showed irregular thickening of the tracheal and left main bronchial walls, suggesting ulceration (lung window, coronal plane, a, arrows). A thick-walled cavity with surrounding nodularity was also present (arrows). These findings improved markedly after TB treatment, as shown on follow-up CT obtained 2 months later (lung window, coronal plane, b) (Wetscherek et al., 2022).

Extrapulmonary Tuberculosis

TB involving sites outside the lungs is termed extrapulmonary tuberculosis. The most common sites are the lymph nodes and pleura, although it can occur almost anywhere in the body. Extrapulmonary TB accounts for a substantial proportion of TB cases worldwide (Baykan et al., 2022). Patients with both pulmonary and extrapulmonary TB are usually classified as having pulmonary TB. For example, miliary TB is classified as pulmonary TB because the lungs are involved. In contrast, tuberculous intrathoracic lymphadenitis involving the mediastinal and/or hilar nodes, or tuberculous pleural effusion without parenchymal lung abnormalities on radiography, is classified as extrapulmonary TB (J. Y. Lee, 2015).

In recent decades, extrapulmonary TB has increased in developed countries, unlike pulmonary TB, which has declined. Even so, extrapulmonary TB

is often not included in TB control programs, likely because of its lower transmissibility (Rolo et al., 2023).

Extrapulmonary TB may involve lymph nodes, the gastrointestinal tract, peritoneum, and solid organs. It may result from reactivation of latent TB, ingestion of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* through infected pulmonary secretions, unpasteurized dairy products, or undercooked meat, hematogenous spread from an adjacent focus, or spread through infected ducts and lymphatics (Debi, 2014; Ladumor et al., 2021).

Tuberculous Meningitis

The diagnosis of tuberculous meningitis (TBM) remains challenging and is based on a combination of clinical features, imaging findings, and cerebrospinal fluid abnormalities. These include detection of acid-fast bacilli on direct cerebrospinal fluid smear or positive cerebrospinal fluid culture, together with clinical or cerebrospinal fluid response to antituberculous therapy. However, clinical features are often nonspecific, and microbiologic confirmation is difficult because cerebrospinal fluid is typically paucibacillary. Imaging plays a central role in diagnosing TBM and detecting its complications early. Sequelae of tuberculous meningitis include focal or diffuse cerebral atrophy, gliosis secondary to infarction, hydrocephalus, meningeal or ependymal calcification, and occasionally syringomyelia (Raut et al., 2016).

Characteristic imaging findings on CT and MRI include basal meningeal enhancement, hydrocephalus, tuberculomas, and infarction. Basal exudates in TBM may appear mildly hyperdense on non-contrast CT and show intense, homogeneous post-contrast enhancement. On MRI, they appear hyperintense on fluid-attenuated inversion recovery images and enhance strongly on post-contrast T1-weighted images. Linear enhancement along the ventricular margins supports the diagnosis of ependymitis. MRI is superior to CT for detecting suspected meningitis and its associated complications. Magnetization transfer imaging has also been reported to be superior for distinguishing TBM from other causes of non-tuberculous meningitis. In TBM, the meninges appear markedly hyperintense on pre-contrast T1-weighted magnetization transfer images and

show further enhancement after contrast administration. The magnetization transfer ratio in TBM is significantly higher than in viral meningitis, whereas fungal and pyogenic meningitis show higher ratios than TBM. In patients with AIDS, meningeal enhancement may be minimal or absent, likely because of an impaired immune response (Raut et al., 2016).

Figure 8. Post-contrast axial (A) and sagittal (B) CT images show enhancing basal exudates (thin arrows) and hydrocephalus (thick arrows) in a proven case of tuberculous meningitis (Raut et al., 2016).

Figure 9. Tuberculous meningitis. Post-contrast axial T1-weighted MR image shows extensive basal leptomeningeal enhancement (thin arrows) with dilatation of the temporal horns. An enhancing tuberculoma (thick arrow) is seen in the right occipital lobe (Raut et al., 2016).

Tuberculous Lymphadenitis

Tuberculous lymphadenitis (TBL) is a localized manifestation of systemic disease and the most common clinical presentation of extrapulmonary TB. It accounts for nearly 35% of extrapulmonary TB cases. TBL may occur during primary TB infection, from reactivation of a dormant focus, or by direct spread from an adjacent site. Cervical lymph nodes are most commonly involved, reported in 60% to 90% of patients, with or without other lymphoid involvement. Mediastinal and axillary lymph node involvement is also common. The rising frequency of extrapulmonary TB, especially lymphadenitis, has been linked to HIV infection (Ladumor et al., 2021; Raut et al., 2016).

Superficial nodal involvement is followed by progressive multiplication of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. Delayed hypersensitivity leads to hyperemia, swelling, necrosis, and central caseation, with inflammation and matting of adjacent nodes. Adherence to the overlying skin may cause induration, and the soft caseous material may eventually rupture into surrounding tissue through

sinus tract formation. The clinical presentation of tuberculous lymphadenitis is variable and may mimic neoplasia or sarcoidosis. Early diagnosis improves treatment outcomes (Ladumor et al., 2021).

On neck ultrasonography, TBL typically appears as multiple hypoechoic, multiloculated cystic nodal conglomerates with thick capsules and surrounding fat stranding. Ultrasound is also useful for image-guided aspiration, cytology, and biopsy. On CT, affected nodes appear as conglomerate lymphadenopathy with central low attenuation and thick, irregular contrast enhancement (Raut et al., 2016). The imaging appearance of TBL reflects disease stage. The early lymphoid hyperplasia stage shows homogeneous nodal enlargement. With progression, central caseous necrosis develops, producing low-attenuation nodes with peripheral capsular rim enhancement. Capsular breakdown leads to fusion of adjacent nodes, resulting in multiloculated enhancement. In late stages, after treatment or healing, fibrosis develops and calcification may be seen. Enlarged nodes in TBL usually show limited growth, typically measuring 12-40 mm. On ultrasound, TBL may also appear as round or oval enlarged lymph nodes with central hypoechoic areas.

Figure 10. Tuberculous cervical lymphadenitis. Left parasagittal CT image shows a large conglomerate of necrotic jugular lymphadenopathy with peripheral rim enhancement (white arrows) (Raut et al., 2016).

Figure 11. Contrast-enhanced CT shows multiple necrotic lymph nodes in the (A) mediastinum, (B) retrocrural region, and (C) mesentery/omentum (arrows), as well as necrotic retroperitoneal lymph nodes (arrows), all with low central attenuation and peripheral capsular rim enhancement. A small right pleural effusion is also visible in image A (Ladumor et al., 2021).

Gastrointestinal Tuberculosis

Gastrointestinal (GI) TB is an uncommon form of abdominal TB and the sixth most common form of extrapulmonary TB. It may involve any part of the GI tract from the esophagus to the rectum. Three main forms are described: (i) the ulcerative type (60%), characterized by single or multiple mucosal ulcers, usually in the jejunum and ileum; (ii) the ulcero-hypertrophic type (30%), characterized by bowel wall thickening with ulceration; and (iii) the hypertrophic type (10%), characterized by scarring and fibrosis, usually involving the ileum and cecum. Complications are similar across all three forms and include perforation, bleeding, fistula formation, and bowel obstruction caused by strictures or mural hypertrophy (Malikowski et al., 2018).

Plain abdominal radiographs are nonspecific and are usually obtained during acute exacerbations. Dilated bowel loops with multiple air-fluid levels suggest bowel obstruction. Pneumoperitoneum may be seen in bowel perforation. Generalized increased abdominal opacity with centrally displaced gas-filled bowel loops suggests ascites. Associated calcified mesenteric lymph nodes and hepatosplenomegaly may also be seen (Malikowski et al., 2018).

Barium contrast studies remain a mainstay in the diagnosis of intestinal TB and have been reported to be useful in 75% of suspected cases. Barium

swallow may show mucosal irregularity, ulceration, traction diverticula, and stricture formation. Sinus tracts and fistulous communication with the mediastinum or tracheobronchial tree may also be demonstrated. Early ileocecal TB appears as spasm and hypermotility with edema of the ileocecal valve. Thickening of the ileocecal valve may be associated with narrowing of the terminal ileum. The terminal ileal mucosa becomes thickened and nodular. As disease progresses, the distal ileum becomes thickened, rigid, and straight, often with complete loss of the normal mucosal pattern. The ileocecal valve becomes thickened and may project into the cecum as a mass. Fixation of bowel loops results in loss of the normal ileocecal angle. The valve becomes incompetent and gaping. Associated granulation and ulceration further distort the valve. A gaping ileocecal valve with narrowing of the terminal ileum produces the inverted umbrella appearance on barium study, known as the Fleischner sign. The cecum becomes scarred, contracted, and conical. Rapid passage of barium from the diseased ileum into the ascending colon through a widely open ileocecal valve is called the Stierlin sign. On barium studies, hypertrophic lesions may produce an hourglass appearance, with dilatation of normal bowel proximally and distally (P. Gupta et al., 2019; Ladumor et al., 2021).

Fluoroscopy and double-contrast barium studies are more useful for evaluating mucosal detail and early ulceration. On fluoroscopic palpation, the involved bowel loops remain fixed and unchanged in position on supine, prone, and standing views. Fixed, dilated loops also show delayed barium transit. Small-bowel enteroclysis provides optimal luminal distention and better mucosal detail, with the added advantage of detecting and characterizing low-grade strictures (P. Gupta et al., 2019).

Figure 12. Ileal tuberculosis. Small-bowel barium study shows cecal scarring and contraction with terminal ileal stricture (black arrow) and associated proximal ileal dilatation (Raut et al., 2016).

CT is the modality of choice for evaluating abdominal TB. Mural thickening in the ileocecal region is common in GI TB. It may be limited to the terminal ileum or cecum, or involve both. Thickening may be symmetric or asymmetric. Asymmetric thickening of the ileocecal valve and medial cecal wall may extend into the cecum and encase the terminal ileum. Fat stranding and inflammation are often present in the adjacent pericecal region and mesentery. Bowel obstruction and perforation may also occur. CT enteroclysis can accurately detect short-segment strictures with concentric mural thickening and homogeneous mural enhancement. CT findings that support the diagnosis of TB include high-density ascites, confluent necrotic abdominal lymphadenopathy, and omental or mesenteric thickening (P. Gupta et al., 2019).

Figure 13. Tuberculous stricture. Coronal post-contrast CT image of the abdomen shows a short-segment, high-grade small-bowel stricture (thin arrow) causing small-bowel obstruction (Raut et al., 2016).

Hepatosplenic Tuberculosis

Hepatosplenic TB results from hematogenous spread from an active TB focus elsewhere in the body. It usually presents as part of miliary TB associated with miliary pulmonary disease. Miliary hepatosplenic TB appears on CT as hepatomegaly with multiple small low-attenuation foci without significant contrast enhancement. The macronodular form is rare and appears as multiple ill-defined hypodense lesions, sometimes with minimal internal enhancement. Thin peripheral rim enhancement is typically seen. Calcified hepatosplenic granulomas may support the diagnosis. On MRI, macronodular lesions are T1 hypointense and variably T2 hypointense to hyperintense, with thin peripheral and/or internal septal enhancement. These lesions may liquefy and form tuberculous abscesses (Jin et al., 2020).

Figure 14. Hepatosplenic tuberculosis. Post-contrast axial abdominal CT image shows multiple hypodense focal granulomas in the liver and spleen (thin arrows). Multiple conglomerate necrotic lymph nodes (thick arrows) are seen at the porta hepatis, extending into the pancreas (Raut et al., 2016).

Genitourinary Tuberculosis

The genitourinary system is one of the most common sites of extrapulmonary TB, accounting for about 15% to 20% of cases. The kidney, prostate, and seminal vesicles are the main primary sites of genitourinary tuberculosis (GUTB). Other genital organs, including the epididymis and bladder, may become involved through ascending or descending spread of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* from other parts of the genitourinary tract. GUTB is rare in children and more common in the second to fourth decades of life. About 25% of patients with GUTB have a history of prior pulmonary TB. Symptoms are often nonspecific, which can delay diagnosis (Mantica et al., 2021).

Patients may present with urinary frequency, dysuria, sterile pyuria, microscopic or gross hematuria, and back, pelvic, or abdominal pain, in addition to systemic symptoms. Detection of *M. tuberculosis* in urine by microbiologic, cytopathologic, or histopathologic methods confirms the diagnosis of GUTB. Sterile pyuria is a classic finding. However, urine smear and culture often fail to detect mycobacteria, likely because bacillary shedding in urine is intermittent and smear interpretation is observer dependent. Direct smear is positive in only 30%

of patients, and urine culture requires 6 to 8 weeks using specialized media. Therefore, in patients with suspected GUTB, imaging plays a central role in diagnosis (Mantica et al., 2021).

Radiographic detection of calcification related to renal TB is relatively uncommon. On plain radiographs, amorphous, granular, or curvilinear renal calcifications may be seen in 24% to 44% of patients. Granulomatous masses involving an entire renal lobe may appear as focal globular calcification. Triangular ring-shaped calcification within the collecting system suggests papillary necrosis. Homogeneous ground-glass calcified caseous tissue is often referred to as putty kidney. Calcification may also be seen in the ureter. Upper ureteric calcification associated with other renal calcifications strongly suggests GUTB. Additional mesenteric lymph node calcification or spinal TB on plain radiographs may support the diagnosis. Renal calcification is associated with a poorer prognosis and, if untreated, may progress with increasing calcification and declining renal function (Malikowski et al., 2018).

Figure 15. Putty kidney. Plain abdominal radiograph shows a calcified, atrophic left kidney caused by tuberculosis (arrow) (Raut et al., 2016).

Depending on the severity of renal involvement, intravenous urography may show a wide range of findings. Up to 10% to 15% of active renal TB cases have normal intravenous urography findings. In early disease, minimal calyceal

dilatation or mild blunting of the calyces due to mucosal edema may be seen. As the disease progresses, the calyceal margins become irregular, indistinct, or ragged, producing a feathery or moth-eaten appearance caused by necrotizing papillitis. Combined direct tissue destruction and ischemia lead to papillary necrosis in genitourinary TB (GUTB). Small papillary cavities may enlarge into medullary cavities that communicate with the adjacent collecting system, forming irregular contrast-filled cavities. With papillary cavitation, infection extends into the urothelium and submucosa of the calyces, causing infundibular stenosis. This may result in localized caliectasis or incomplete calyceal opacification and, in advanced cases, hydronephrosis. Sharp angulation of the renal pelvis results from ureteral scarring. Early findings include ureteral dilatation and mucosal irregularity, known as a saw-tooth ureter, which may progress to ureteral narrowing and shortening, known as a pipe-stem ureter. Multiple ureteral strictures may produce a beaded or corkscrew appearance (Malikowski et al., 2018).

Cross-sectional CT is highly useful for evaluating a nonfunctioning kidney and accurately defining disease extent and perinephric spread. With multidetector CT, multiphase post-contrast imaging and multiplanar reconstruction can be performed. CT urography better depicts the pathologic anatomy of the entire urinary tract. CT is also valuable for detecting complications and involvement of other abdominal organs. Fine calcifications that may be missed on plain radiographs are much better seen on CT. Careful review of post-contrast corticomedullary and nephrographic phase images is important to assess renal parenchymal and collecting system involvement in GUTB. Tuberculous granulomas vary in size and usually appear as hypodense lesions with minimal or mild peripheral enhancement after contrast. Associated collecting system abnormalities may also be present. Larger nodules may show heterogeneous density and mimic renal neoplasms. Rarely, renal TB appears as a well-defined cystic mass with thick septa. Local hypoperfusion caused by tissue edema and vasoconstriction, similar to acute pyelonephritis, may also be seen in renal TB (Raut et al., 2016).

Figure 16. CT intravenous urography shows delayed excretion by the right kidney and a left ureter with multiple kinks and stenoses (Mantica et al., 2021).

MRI may be used to characterize lesions in pediatric or pregnant patients, or when ionizing radiation and iodinated contrast are contraindicated. MRI can provide detailed evaluation of renal morphology, the pelvicalyceal system and ureters, the bladder, and the genital organs. Non-contrast MR urography is particularly useful for evaluating abnormalities of the pelvicalyceal system and ureters in patients with renal failure (Kapoor et al., 2008).

Figure 17. Tuberculous epididymo-orchitis in a patient with known pulmonary tuberculosis. (A, B) Ultrasound of the right testis shows an ill-defined hypoechoic lesion and an enlarged epididymis with peripheral vascularity. MRI shows an ill-defined hypointense lesion on T2-weighted imaging (C), an intermediate-signal lesion on T1-weighted imaging (D), and multifocal peripheral enhancement involving the epididymal head and a thickened right spermatic cord (E, F) (Ladumor et al., 2021).

Musculoskeletal Tuberculosis

Musculoskeletal TB is an uncommon form of extrapulmonary TB, accounting for 1% to 3% of all tuberculosis infections. Tuberculous spondylitis is the most common form, representing about 50% of cases. Extraspinal musculoskeletal TB includes peripheral tuberculous arthritis (60%), osteomyelitis (38%), and soft tissue TB, including tenosynovitis and bursitis (Leonard & Blumberg, 2017).

Plain radiography is insensitive for early detection of tuberculous spondylitis, as 30% to 50% of bone destruction is required before osteolytic changes become visible. Early findings include indistinct endplates, loss of the

sclerotic margin, and irregularity or erosion of the endplates. Lytic lesions in the vertebral body usually lack peripheral sclerosis. Disc involvement is marked by reduced disc space. Two adjacent vertebral bodies and the intervening disc are typically involved. As the disease progresses, anterior wedging and vertebral collapse may produce the characteristic gibbus deformity. Subligamentous spread may cause scalloping of the anterior vertebral margins. Paravertebral soft tissue involvement appears as displacement of the paraspinal line in the thoracic region and outward bulging or obscuration of the psoas shadow. Calcification within a paraspinal abscess, when present, is pathognomonic of tuberculosis (Abid et al., 2024).

CT is useful for evaluating early bone destruction, the pattern of bony involvement, and associated calcification in hypodense paraspinal soft tissue. Fragmented bone destruction is more common on CT. CT is also often used to guide transpedicular vertebral biopsy for histopathology and culture or sensitivity testing. When multiple adjacent vertebral bodies have collapsed, CT helps identify the involved vertebrae accurately by counting the posterior elements without corresponding vertebral bodies. CT is also useful for assessing spinal deformity (Abid et al., 2024; Raut et al., 2016).

Figure 18. Sagittal CT image (A) shows irregular destruction of the adjacent endplates of the T11 and T12 vertebral bodies with reduced T11-T12

intervertebral disc height and mild adjacent sclerosis (black arrow) in a young woman receiving treatment for tuberculous spondylitis. Associated abnormal prevertebral and epidural soft tissue is also seen (thin white arrows). Coronal CT image (B) shows a small focus of peripheral calcification in a left psoas abscess (thick white arrow), which is pathognomonic of tuberculosis.

MRI is the modality of choice for evaluating tuberculous spondylitis because it detects early marrow and paraspinal soft tissue changes and provides multiplanar imaging with excellent soft tissue contrast. Early findings include focal T2 hyperintense and T1 hypointense marrow edema in the anterior vertebral body adjacent to the endplates, with heterogeneous post-contrast enhancement. Disease progression leads to cortical and endplate destruction, subligamentous spread, disc involvement, and vertebral body destruction. The affected disc space becomes narrowed and shows abnormal T2 hyperintense signal. Subligamentous spread may involve several adjacent vertebrae while preserving the intervening disc spaces. This is commonly associated with paravertebral and epidural collections, which are T2 hyperintense and T1 hypointense with thin, smooth peripheral post-contrast enhancement. MRI also clearly demonstrates multifocal TB, spinal cord compression, abnormal T2 hyperintense cord signal, and foraminal or neural compromise caused by epidural collections. The full extent of iliopsoas and paraspinal abscesses can also be shown on MRI and may extend to the proximal thigh. Posterior element involvement is not uncommon. Cross-sectional imaging, including CT and MRI, is especially useful for detecting small foci of infection in the posterior elements (Raut et al., 2016).

Figure 19. Subligamentous spread and paraspinal abscess. Sagittal T2-weighted (A) and T1-weighted (B) images show tuberculous spondylodiscitis at L4-L5 with T2 hyperintense and T1 isointense epidural soft tissue causing indentation of the cauda equina. Adjacent L1, L2, and L3 vertebral bodies are involved due to subligamentous spread (thin arrows), with preservation of the intervening intervertebral discs. Post-contrast sagittal (C) and coronal (D) T1-weighted images show thin, smooth peripheral enhancement of prevertebral, epidural, and bilateral iliopsoas abscesses (thick arrows), a characteristic feature of tuberculosis (Raut et al., 2016).

Pyogenic spondylitis is the most important differential diagnosis. Features that favor tuberculous rather than pyogenic spondylitis include thin, smooth peripheral enhancement of paraspinal collections, well-defined paraspinal soft tissue, subligamentous spread across three or more vertebral levels, involvement of multiple vertebrae, skip lesions, relatively late disc destruction, absence of sclerosis, thoracic spine involvement, and calcification within a paraspinal abscess, which is pathognomonic. Other atypical infections, including brucellosis, fungal infection, and sarcoidosis, may produce similar imaging findings. When

the infectious process is limited to the vertebral body and paraspinal soft tissue, the differential diagnosis includes metastasis, myeloma, and lymphoma (Ladumor et al., 2021).

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